

(pH 4.3) of 20 ml of .2M KVO_3 , 7 ml of glacial acetic acid and 40 ml of .013M $K[Sb(OH)_6]$ after an interval of twelve days, following the same treatment as has been described for the synthesis of the ammonium salt. From analysis : (Found V, 25.344; Sb, 5.051; K, 11.317; H, 3.798 per cent. Calcd for $K_7[SbV_{12}O_{36}] \cdot 46H_2O$: V, 25.383; Sb, 5.060; K, 11.323; H, 3.815 per cent. Potassium was estimated by flame photometric method.

Molecular Weight Determination—The molecular weights of all the salts of $[SbV_{12}O_{36}]^{7-}$ heteropoly anion, were successfully determined by the methods as has been done by Alexander⁷ and by Thilo and Krüger⁸ for the molecular weight determinations of certain inorganic polyacids and polyphosphates etc, in water and molten sodium sulphate decahydrate. This determination showed the molecular weights of the compounds $(NH_4)_7[SbV_{12}O_{36}] \cdot 28H_2O$, $Na_7[SbV_{12}O_{36}] \cdot 18H_2O$ and $K_7[SbV_{12}O_{36}] \cdot 46H_2O$ to be 1905, 1760 and 2375, as compared with the calculated values 1940, 1795 and 2411 respectively, which are in the range of fair agreement.

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Studies on 3-Bromo-2-Hydroxy-5-Methylacetophenone Oxime (BHMAO) as Metal Complexing Agent : Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium (II), Copper (II), Nickel (II) and Cobalt (II)

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IN continuation of our studies on orthophenolic oximes^{1,2}, the present work reports the use of newly synthesized 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone oxime (BHMAO) for the spectrophotometric determination of microgram quantities of Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II). The method can also be employed in the determination of Cu(II) and Ni(II) in a mixture directly.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents : A systronic spectrophotometer (type 103) was employed for recording spectra. The pH values of the solutions were measured with a systronic pH meter (type 322).

Standard stock solutions of palladium (II), copper (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II) were prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of B.D.H. (AnalaR grade) $PdCl_2$, $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$, $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ in double distilled water containing dilute hydrochloric acid (0.5N) and standardized gravimetrically³. Ammonium hydroxide-ammonium chloride and acetic acid-sodium acetate were used to prepare buffers of different pH values.

The oxime of 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone⁴ was prepared by refluxing its ethanolic solution with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and anhydrous sodium acetate for about two hours and purified by repeated crystallization from ethanol m.p. 198°.

Results and Discussion

It has been observed that the complexes can be extracted into nonaqueous solvents such as chloroform, carbontetrachloride, ethylacetate etc. The colours of the extracted complexes of Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) are yellow, buff, green and yellow respectively. Subsequent studies have been carried out in chloroform, because the extraction was better in chloroform than other nonaqueous solvents.

The method of Vosburg and Cooper⁵ was employed to determine the maximum absorption (λ_{max}) and number of the complexes. The absorption measurements show that only one complex is formed which has λ_{max} (nm) 400, 640, 600 and 400 for Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes respectively.

Effect of pH :

A series of solutions (metal : ligand in 1:4) varying in pH was prepared and the absorbances were recorded after extraction of the complexes into chloroform at their λ_{max} . The range of pH value for no change in absorbance are reported in Table 1. The absorbance of the solutions decrease at higher or lower pH values.

Effect of reagent and ethanol concentration :

It was found that 6 fold excess of the reagent is necessary to attain the full colour development in all the cases under study. The reagent has negligible absorbance at the wave lengths selected for the measurements. The extracted complexes were found to be exhibit constant absorbance for atleast 48 hours.

It was also observed that the extraction of the complexes into chloroform depends upon the concentration of ethanol in aqueous medium. Above 30% (V/V) ethanol, the complex does not completely pass into chloroform layer in one extraction. In view of this 25% (V/V) concentration of ethanol was maintained throughout the work.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF CHELATES OF Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II) AND Co(II) WITH BHMAO

Characteristics	Pd(II)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Co(II)
Colour	Yellow	Buff	Green	Yellow
λ_{max} (nm)	400]	640	600	400
pH range	1.5–5.0	4.0–8.5	5.0–8.0	7.0–8.5
Selected pH	2.5	5.5	6.5	7.5
Composition (M : L)	1 : 2	1 : 2	1 : 2	1 : 2
Stability constant	6.8×10^7	4.2×10^7	3.28×10^7	2.525×10^7
Free energy constant (Kcal mole ⁻¹)	10.77	10.48	10.33	10.18
Beer's law range (ppm)	7.42–51.94	8–64	5.87–52.83	3.6–54.0
Molar extinction coefficient	1000	170	84	640
Sensitivity (ppm)(log I ₀ /I=0.001)	0.106	0.400	0.587	0.180

Composition and stability constant of the complexes :

Job's method of continuous variation⁶ was employed. The solutions were mixed in different proportions keeping the total molarity constant. The suitable pH was adjusted (Table 1) of the aqueous phase and the absorbance was measured of extracted complexes in chloroform. The curves between absorbance and metal ion concentration indicate the formation of complexes in which the metal ligand ratio is 1:2. This conclusion is also supported by the mole ratio⁷ and slope ratio⁸ methods.

The stability constants of the complexes were calculated from the data of the mole ratio method using the usual expressions. The values are reported in Table 1. The changes in free energy (k cal mole⁻¹) of the complex formation were also calculated at 27° and reported in Table 1.

Beer's law and physical constants :

The validity of Beer's law (ppm) and sensitivity (metal cm⁻²) of the reactions for log I₀/I=0.001 were calculated and reported in Table 1. The relative mean error was found to be 0.3-0.6%.

General procedure for the determination of metal ions :

A suitable aliquot of metal ion solution containing 20-50 µg of metal ion was introduced on a 100 ml separatory funnel, adjusted to suitable pH value (Table 1) and sufficient excess of the reagent was added to it and mixed thoroughly. The mixture was allowed to stand for 5 minutes. The precipitated complex was extracted 2-3 times with 5 ml portions of chloroform. The extracts were collected in a 25 ml volumetric flask, diluted to the mark with chloroform and the absorbance was measured at λ_{max} against appropriate reagent blank prepared under similar conditions.

Effect of diverse ions :

The influence of diverse ions on the determination of the metal ions using BHMAO was also studied in the usual manner. The difference of ±2% in absorbance value was arbitrarily taken as an interference.

In the case of palladium(II) and copper(II) at 50 ppm ; 2000 ppm CH₃COO⁻, NO₃⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, SO₄²⁻ ; 1000 ppm Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ca²⁺, Be²⁺, Cd²⁺, Mg²⁺, Fe³⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, I⁻, 500 ppm Cr³⁺, citrate, tartrate and 100 ppm Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mn²⁺ could be tolerated. But Fe³⁺, VO²⁺, UO₂²⁺ and VO₃⁻ interfere seriously.

In the case of nickel(II) at 50 ppm ; 2000 ppm Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, CH₃COO⁻ ; 1000 ppm Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, I⁻ ; 500 ppm Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, citrate, tartrate, 200 ppm Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ could be tolerated. However, Cu²⁺, Pd²⁺, Fe³⁺, UO₂²⁺, Mn²⁺ and Co²⁺ interfere seriously.

In the case of cobalt(II) at 50 ppm ; 1000 ppm Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, CH₃COO⁻, SO₄²⁻ ; 500 ppm Ca²⁺, Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺, Zn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Cd²⁺ could be tolerated. But Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Pd²⁺, Fe³⁺, Mn²⁺ interfere seriously.

Simultaneous determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) :

There is a difference of 40 nm in the wavelengths of λ_{max} of the Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes. In view of this the following equations derived by Sandell⁹ for simultaneous determination of the two components were employed for the determination of Cu(II) (A) and Ni(II)(B) :

$$E_1^A C_A + E_1^B C_B = A_1 \text{ (Total absorbance at 640 nm)}$$

$$E_2^A C_A + E_2^B C_B = A_2 \text{ (Total absorbance at 600 nm)}$$

where E_1^A, E_2^A and E_1^B, E_2^B the molar extinction coefficients for Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes at 640 nm and 600 nm respectively are $170(E_1^A)$, $125(E_2^A)$, $84(E_1^B)$ and $70(E_2^B)$ $\text{l mole}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. The results for the determination of Cu(II) and Ni(II) in synthetic mixtures of the two are quite satisfactory.

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Bromatometric Estimation of Ascorbic Acid Using Azine and Oxazine Dyes as Indicators[†]

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THE indicators that have been reported for the bromatometric estimation of ascorbic acid are: *p*-ethoxychrysoidine¹; starch-iodide², aminophenoxazines³, naphthol blue black and variamine blue⁴, and chlorpromazine, promazine, perazine and diethazine⁵. Of these, only *p*-ethoxychrysoidine has been utilised for the titrimetric determination of ascorbic acid in the pure form as well as medicinal preparations¹. The present communication describes the use of eleven azine

and oxazine dyes, Neutral Violet(NV), Neutral Red(NR), Azocarmine G (ACG), Azocarmine B (ACB), Wool Fast Blue GL (WFBGL), Nigrosin (NG), Capri Blue (CB), Solochrome Prune AS (SPAS), Gallamine Blue (GB), Celestine Blue (CLB), and Meldola's Blue (MB) (Colour Index Nos. 50030, 50040, 50085, 50090, 50320, 50420, 51015, 51040, 51045, 51050 and 51175 respectively), as indicators in the titrimetric estimation of ascorbic acid with potassium bromate in hydrochloric and sulphuric acid media and the application of the methods for the determination of ascorbic acid content of commercial vitamin C tablets. In this connection, it may be mentioned that the azine dyes have been used for the titration of arsenic (III) with potassium bromate⁶.

The advantages of the indicators now reported are: (1) they can be added at the beginning of the titration, (2) the titration can be performed even in the absence of added potassium bromide, and (3) three of the indicators, ACG, ACB and WFBGL, function reversibly and can therefore be employed for the reverse titrations, i.e., titrations of potassium bromate with ascorbic acid, also; the indicators reported earlier have to be added towards the close of the titration, presence of added potassium bromide is necessary, and except variamine blue, other indicators are not suitable for the reverse titrations.

Experimental

Approximately 0.1*N* solutions of potassium bromate and ascorbic acid were prepared and standardised. A small quantity (0.5 g per litre) of E.D.T.A. was added as stabiliser for the ascorbic acid solutions. Solutions (0.1%) of the azine and oxazine dyes were prepared in deionised water from the following samples: NV: George T. Gurr, NR: E. Merck, ACG and NG: Fluka, WFBGL: Bayer, CB: Chroma, ACB, SPAS, GB, CLB and MB: E. Gurr.

Procedure:

Ascorbic acid solution (3–10 ml of 0.1 *N*) is treated with enough 1:1 hydrochloric or sulphuric acid, so as to give an acidity of 1.0*M* hydrochloric acid or 2.5*M* (3.0 with SPAS, CB and GB) sulphuric acid when diluted to 50 ml, and the following amount of the indicator solution:

NR, ACG, WFBGL, CB, SPAS, GB and MB: 0.1 ml, ACB and NG: 0.25 ml, NV and CLB: 0.5 ml.

The mixture is then titrated with 0.1 *N* potassium bromate solution and the end point is indicated by the decolourisation of the titration mixture.

The colour changes at the end points are very sharp and the results obtained are in excellent agreement with those obtained by other methods.

The following indicators function satisfactorily in titrations involving dilute (0.01*N*) solutions of ascorbic acid and potassium bromate also.

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